

D4.7 Validation and Evaluation - Final Report

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Executive summary

This document presents the final validation and evaluation results for the Intelligent Services during the third vegetative season (2023). Building upon the initial assessment detailed in deliverable D4.6, this report provides a comprehensive analysis of the 2023 vegetative season, utilizing consistent metrics where applicable to facilitate comparison across the two validation years. Through a combination of quantitative analysis and qualitative feedback from end-users, the report offers valuable insights into the performance of VitiGEOSS services.

The analysis of performance metrics encompasses various aspects, including forecasting vine phenology, monitoring critical crop indicators, providing climate predictions, predicting the onset of vine diseases, delivering precise disease treatment protocols, optimizing resource and task allocation, and evaluating sustainability indicators. Notably, the 2023 season experienced abnormal climatic conditions, which impacted certain results. Despite these challenges, climate forecasts maintained their reliability over the two years of result validation, while phenology forecasts showed slight deviations compared to the 2022 season but remained superior to baseline metrics such as GDD (Growing Degree Days), GFV (Grapevine Flowering Veraison model) and GSR (Grapevine Sugar Ripeness model). Deep Drone service analysis proved to enable precision analysis over the vineyard rows, while key crop indicators affirmed their effectiveness in continuously monitoring the field. Disease forecasting methodology shows promise, but the results lack years of data and require further improvements. Sustainability proved to be a crucial service for tracking information about the field, and business tracking tools have enabled wine growers to optimize vineyard activities efficiently.

This document serves as a valuable tool to validate the outcomes of the previous vegetative season and gather crucial feedback from end-users, further enhancing the refinement of the Intelligent Services.

In summary, this report underscores the unwavering commitment of the VitiGEOSS project to support the winemaking community in refining strategies, embracing sustainable practices, and making well-informed decisions throughout the growing season. Through continuous innovation and collaboration, the Intelligent Services developed within the VitiGEOSS project aspire to revolutionize vineyard management and drive the industry towards a more sustainable and prosperous future.

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List of abbreviations

DM	<i>Downy mildew</i>
DNN	<i>Deep Neural Network</i>
DT	<i>Decision Trees</i>
EC	<i>European Commission</i>
EO	<i>Earth Observation</i>
EU	<i>European Union</i>
GB	<i>Gradient Boosting</i>
GDD	<i>Growing Degree Days</i>
GFV	<i>Grapevine Flowering Veraison</i>
GSR	<i>Grapevine Sugar Ripeness</i>
KNN	<i>K-Nearest Neighbours</i>
LR	<i>Logistic Regression</i>
NB	<i>Naïve Bayes</i>
PM	<i>Powdery mildew</i>
RF	<i>Random Forest</i>
SVM	<i>Support Vector Machines</i>
WP	<i>Work Package</i>
KPI	<i>Key Performance Indicator</i>

Introduction

The VitiGEOSS project continues its mission to develop a comprehensive suite of services designed to empower winemakers with invaluable insights into various facets of vineyard management, spanning weather and climate forecasting, disease and phenology monitoring and forecasting, crop management, and sustainability practices. Leveraging cutting-edge technologies such as satellite imagery, in-field sensors, and aerial imaging, the project aims to deliver Intelligent Services (IS) that furnish essential information crucial for effective vineyard management. Central to this endeavour is the VitiGEOSS decision support system, which plays a pivotal role in enhancing vineyard management processes through the provision of forecasts, provisional models, and advanced visualization tools.

The weather and climate forecast service stands as a cornerstone, offering predictions of atmospheric variables to other services within the platform. This includes deterministic weather forecasts providing three-hourly values for the next three days, as well as probabilistic sub-seasonal and seasonal climate forecasts anticipating atmospheric variable probabilities for the weeks and months ahead. Section 1 provides a review of the accuracy of the data and an analysis of the service during the third vegetative season.

Section 2 is dedicated to phenological cycle monitoring and prediction. In response to weather conditions, it is a critical tool, facilitating informed decisions regarding key agronomic practices like fertilization, pesticide application, irrigation, and harvesting schedules. VitiGEOSS implements various models to provide innovative solutions to phenology tracking, monitoring phases such as bud break, blooming, fruit set, veraison, berry maturity, and leaf fall using data from satellite imagery, weather stations, and climate predictions.

Section 3 presents the drone service, an initially not foreseen service that encounter the end-users' interest. Drone imagery is employed to establish a monitoring system capable of identifying and highlighting areas of the vineyard characterized by lower vigor and water stress, thus enabling spatially variable management considerations.

The key crop indicator service in Section 4 assesses the vegetation health, crop productivity, water use, nitrogen content, crop water demand for the upcoming week, and yield estimates for the season.

Section 5 presents an overview of the performance of the disease monitoring and forecasting models. They utilize statistical and artificial intelligence (AI) techniques calibrated over a vegetative season using real-time data from weather stations, phenological monitoring, and disease quantification.

The business and sustainability management service (Section 6) strives to track important sustainable KPIs and optimize resource utilization by supporting farmers in making decisions conducive to a more sustainable vineyard management strategy, providing informed decision-making support and optimal scheduling of tasks, resources, and personnel.

A summary of the services presented with the data sources adopted are in Table 1.

Table 1 Summary of service models and data sources adopted

Service	Model/algorithm name	Short description	Data sources
Weather and Climate forecast	Weather forecast	Numerical model output	MONARCH
Weather and Climate forecast	Sub-seasonal climate forecast	Post-processing of model output providing probabilistic forecast for the next 4 weeks	NCEP-CFSv2 ERA5 ERA5-Land

Weather and Climate forecast	Seasonal climate forecast	Post-processing of model output providing probabilistic forecast for the next 3 months	ECMWF SEAS5 ERA5 ERA5Land
Phenology	Deep EO3	Phenological monitoring through satellite data	Copernicus Sentinel-3
Phenology	Deep CAM	Phenological monitoring through in-field cameras. Used for <i>a posteriori</i> validation.	In-field cameras
Phenology	Deep Weather Observations	Phenological monitoring through weather station data	In field weather stations (temperature)
Phenology	Deep Weather Forecast	Phenological forecast	- Weather stations (temperature) - Short term weather predictions - Climate prediction
Phenology	Mechanistic	Phenological forecast	- Weather stations (temperature, rain accumulation, solar radiation) - Short term weather predictions - Climate prediction
Diseases	Short-term diseases	Short-term disease forecast	- Weather stations - Field observations - Short term weather predictions - Phenology models
Diseases	Sub-seasonal diseases	Short-term disease forecast	- Weather stations - Field observations - Climate prediction - Phenology models
Diseases	Seasonal diseases	Short-term disease forecast	- Weather stations - Field observations - Climate prediction - Phenology models
Business and sustainability	Task scheduler	Task and work team scheduler	- User data
Business and sustainability	Sustainability KPIs	Sustainability indication and tracking	- User sustainability data - Machinery data - Satellite images
Drone	Deep drone	Vegetation indexes of high-resolution images	- Aerial high resolution RGB orthoimages
Crop Parameters	ETlook	Algorithm for evapotranspiration and biomass data	Sentinel-2 Weather data
Crop Water Demand	CWD model	Water need forecast	ETlook Weather forecast
Yield estimation	Random Forest and Gradient Boosting	Yield prediction next season	Historical yield data

The deliverable focuses on the evaluation of these services during the third vegetative season (year 2023), building upon the groundwork laid out in the second vegetative season (year 2022) presented in D4.6. For a more comprehensive understanding of the services, refer to D2.2 and D2.3.

In addition to the technical evaluations and performance assessments, it is important to underscore the significance of incorporating end users' feedback into the evaluation process. Feedback from end users serves as a crucial component in understanding the real-world utility and effectiveness of the Intelligent Services developed within the VitiGEOSS project. Throughout the evaluation period, end users' feedback has been collected through various methods to ensure a comprehensive understanding of their perspectives and experiences. These methods include written feedback sent directly to the service providers, one-to-one interviews conducted with individual users of the platform, and plenary discussions held among both end users and service providers. By actively soliciting and incorporating feedback from end users, the VitiGEOSS project aims to iteratively refine and enhance its services to better meet the diverse needs and requirements of vineyard managers and stakeholders.

As for the second vegetative season, the pilot plots utilized for data collection are situated at three demo sites:

- Portugal (Symington): Quinta do Ataíde and Quinta do Bomfim.
- Spain (Torres): Aranyó and Sant Martí Sarroca.
- Italy (Mastroberardino): Mirabella Eclano, Montefusco, Montemarano, Pietradefusi, and Santa Paolina.

Further details about the pilot plots and the data collected in 2023, utilized in the validation presented in this document, can be found in D4.3.

1. Weather and climate forecasting services

In the VitiGEOSS climate forecast service, the model outputs for a set of variables are post-processed to provide the probabilities in three categories (Figure 1): below-normal, normal, or above-normal conditions. Details were provided in previous deliverables (D4.6 and D4.2).

Figure 1. Design of the climate forecast visualisation created during the project mock-ups. An idealised sub-seasonal forecast initialised on the 13th of May 2021 shows the air temperature forecast for the next four weeks.

The assessment of the climate forecast products is done by calculating statistics, called skill scores, that compare the performance of two forecasts. The aim is to inform the user if the climate forecast provided as part of the vitiGEOSS services shows added value compared to using an alternative forecast. The alternative forecast here considered is the climatological forecast, which is a forecast based solely upon the climatological statistics from past observations. This assessment is delivered along with the operational forecast. The reason is that the climate forecasts at these time scales lose information from the initial conditions. Although the state-of-the-art climate models include information from other components than the atmosphere of the climate system (e.g. surface ocean temperatures), the added value can be low when compared to climatological information depending on the location, initialisation date and forecast time. Therefore, this skill score is computed for each location, initialization date and forecast time, and it is tailored to the product provided. In the case of the VitiGEOSS climate forecast service, the products are based on tercile categories, and the skill score computed is the Rank Probability Skill Score (RPSS; Wilks, 2011) for these categories, which measures resolution, reliability and uncertainty -three key forecast attributes for decision-makers. When the skill score is positive the forecast provided is better than the climatological forecast. In case the skill score is not positive, the bars in the plot are blurred, as shown in the second forecast week of Figure 1; the user is informed and can use the climatology, i.e. equal probable categories.

Given the novelty of including sub-seasonal climate forecasts in the climate services for sustainability vineyard management, the detection of the windows of opportunity at sub-seasonal timescales has been considered during 2023. This analysis has been carried out by exploring the periods when the skill score was higher than 0. In that case, the locations where vineyard plots are located have been selected, and the skill scores of each site have been mapped as a function of the initialization date and the forecasted week. An example has been chosen given the number of combinations and the generally good performance of the sub-seasonal forecast for the products provided.

As expected, the skill scores decrease when the forecast week (lead time) increases, since the forecast loses the predictive skill brought by the initial conditions (Figure 2). The skill score of 2-metre air temperature in the selected locations shows positive values during most of the year, except for a few weeks in early summer and winter.

Even with this lack of positive skill, the sub-seasonal climate forecast can be handy because it performs well for spring and autumn, which are very relevant seasons for managing vineyards. For other variables, the results are similar, except for the accumulated precipitation forecast which shows less skilful predictions, especially in summer (see Annex 2).

2-metre air temperature / RPSS / 1999-2016

Figure 2. 2-metre air temperature skill scores (RPSS; in percentage) by forecast week for all initialization dates in 2023 and two locations in Campania (top), Douro (middle), and Catalonia (bottom). White boxes correspond to negative skill scores.

1.1 Evaluation during the operational period

This section includes the evaluation of the service provided from January 2022 until December 2023. The approach followed consists of showing the most likely tercile for each forecast product provided while including the observed tercile (Figure 3).

When the most likely tercile matches the observed tercile, it is considered a hit. For the sub-seasonal forecast of 2-metre air temperature 1 week in advance in a relevant location in Catalonia, 68 hits out of the 103 weeks of forecast evaluated are accounted for. When looking at the forecast 2 weeks ahead, the number of hits decreases to 59 out of 102 weeks.

Figure 3 Most likely tercile category of the operational 2-metre air temperature of the sub-seasonal climate forecast products from January 2022 to December 2023 at a relevant location in Catalonia for the forecast 1 (top) and 2 (bottom) weeks in advance. For each p

The most likely tercile evaluation products differ from the RPSS. The RPSS is calculated in a reference period in the past and therefore it can be provided along with the operational climate products. The most likely tercile evaluation can only be calculated after the forecast is released and the observations are made available.

Furthermore, the period to compute the RPSS at each location, initialisation date and forecast time is around 20 years (1999-2016 for the sub-seasonal climate forecast and 1993-2016 for the seasonal climate forecast). In the case of the most likely tercile evaluation, only 1 or 2 observations are available during the operational service (2022-2023) for each location, initialisation date and forecast time.

We should also take into account that climate forecasts are probabilistic products, while this visualisation mechanism illustrates a deterministic assessment, showing whether the most probable tercile has been observed. However, the probabilistic climate forecasts are more flexible than the deterministic approach of hitting the most likely tercile. For instance, a user could be concerned about the above-normal category for a given decision. In this situation, the user can compare the probability of one category against the other two categories. Nevertheless, and more importantly, the benefits of taking up the probabilistic climate forecasts materialise in the long term (MacLeod et al., 2021): when the skill is positive, the most-likely tercile forecasted for a specific time and location may be different from the observed, but it has proven to perform better than the climatology for 18 years in the past (24 in the case of the seasonal climate forecast).

The overall performance of the sub-seasonal climate service is shown in Table 2 and includes the percentage of positive RPSS over a year, i.e. 52 initialization dates (as shown in Figure 2), and the percentage of hits during the period January 2022 to December 2023, i.e., 103, 102, 101 and 100 weeks of forecasts for the forecast week 1 to 4, respectively. The number of hits decreases with the forecast time in general. Temperature is the variable with more hits, i.e. the variable for which more times the most likely tercile matched the observed tercile.

Table 2 Percentage of positive RPSS and percentage of forecast hits during the period January 2022 to December 2023, on average, and as a function of the forecast week for the sub-seasonal climate forecasts.

	Percentage of positive RPSS (1999-2016)	Hits (January 2022 - December 2023)
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Variable	week 1	week 2	week 3	week 4	Average	week 1	week 2	week 3	week 4	Average
2-metre air temperature	100.0	95.2	88.8	85.5	92.4	66.7	53.7	55.0	55.3	57.7
Accumulated precipitation	73.1	30.5	30.1	31.9	41.4	52.0	42.3	38.3	39.7	43.1
Solar radiation	98.0	96.8	94.0	98.8	96.9	52.0	43.7	40.0	43.7	44.8

1.2 Exploration of a precipitation-based indicator

In order to follow the best practices when co-developing a climate service (Bojovic et al., 2021), during the last year, BSC kept interacting with users. During the stakeholders meeting in Douro in May 2023 (<https://vitigeoss.eu/local-stakeholder-event-portuguese/>), users pointed out the relevance of the precipitation forecast, given the frequent precipitation events that occurred in Spring 2023 in Italy (International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies, 2023). Figure 4 shows the most likely tercile category of the operational accumulated weekly precipitation of the sub-seasonal climate forecast products from January 2022 to July 2023 at a relevant location in the Campania region for the forecast one week in advance. For each panel, the top row represents the above-normal category, the middle row the normal category and the third row the below-normal category. Dark (light) colours are used for forecasts with positive (negative) skill. Dots represent the observed tercile category. The sub-seasonal precipitation forecast captured the extreme precipitation event from mid-April to the beginning of June 2023, one week in advance.

Figure 4 Most likely tercile category of the operational accumulated weekly precipitation of the sub-seasonal climate forecast products from January 2022 to December 2023 at a relevant location in the Campania region for the forecast one week in advance.

However, users were concerned about continuous precipitation because it could trigger disease development. Therefore, one user defined an extreme precipitation index as 5 consecutive days with more than 10 mm per day. Following this definition, past observations (ERA5; Hersbach et al., 2020) have been explored to understand the frequency of these events. Figure 5, shows the daily accumulated precipitation in the Montemarano from January to July 2023. Although several precipitation events occurred in Spring 2023, none of them followed the index definition.

Figure 5 Daily accumulated precipitation in Montemarrano from January to July 2023 as shown in ERA5 datasets.

The index was also explored for the period 1993-2016 in the Campania region to understand its past frequency of occurrence (Figure 6). Most of the region shows between 0 and 2 events in 24 years, that is the case of Montemarano and surrounding areas. In Salerno, the maximum occurrence was recorded with 34 cases in 24 years.

Figure 6 Frequency of 5 consecutive rainy days above 10 mm of precipitation in the Campania region for the period 1993-2016 using ERA5 reference dataset

These results were presented to two out of the three users and other technical partners in an online meeting in October 2023. The meeting had two objectives: first, to show the index

exploration and discuss the thresholds selected, and second, to confirm with users that the interpretation of the forecast skill provided in the services was practical.

During the meeting, the sources of predictability at sub-seasonal and seasonal time scales were explained, as well as the limitation of these climate forecasts to predicting exact values (by definition, climate forecast aims to predict mean states of climate variables). Attendees reported that they agreed with the representation of the skill in the operational products. Further exploration and discussions are necessary to discuss the potential of the extreme precipitation index.

1.3 End-users feedback

The feedback from stakeholders regarding the Weather and Climate Forecasting Service varied, reflecting differing perspectives and needs. While Torres expressed scepticism about the reliability of climate predictions and their applicability for decision making in their case, Mastroberardino and Symington acknowledged the value and potential of the service, especially in aiding data-driven decision-making for vineyard activities. Despite reservations, all stakeholders recognized the importance of accurate climate forecasting for their operations (Figure 7).

For which operations were the VITIGE OSS forecasts useful?

Figure 7 “For which operations were the VITIGE OSS forecast useful?” Stakeholders answers.

The climate forecast provided by BSC are the state-of-the-art in climate research. Further research will help enhance the reliability and accuracy of predictions, which is crucial for increasing stakeholder trust and usability. Additionally, prioritizing features like frost alerts, which all stakeholders expressed interest in, aligns with their immediate needs and can enhance the service’s relevance and utility. Managing user expectations on the capabilities of climate predictions and training on how to use even unskilful predictions is also crucial to ensure the uptake of the service.

Overall, stakeholders expressed willingness to continue using the service. By focusing on enhancing prediction accuracy, providing tailored features such as frost alerts, and fostering continuous dialogue with users, the Weather and Climate Forecasting Service can evolve into an indispensable tool for informed decision-making in vineyard management.

2. Phenology services

This section presents the validation of the phenological models for the third vegetative season within the VITIGEOSS project. The phenological models are crucial components of the intelligent services developed for monitoring and forecasting crop growth stages. These models are categorized into detection models, which monitor the current phenological status of the crop, and forecast models, which predict the upcoming phenological phases up to four weeks in advance. The models are based on the historical data of the varieties Syrah, Touriga Nacional, Touriga Franca, Aglianico and Greco (this last cultivar only for the mechanistic model that requires less historical data for the calibration process).

The models for predicting and detecting the occurrence of phenological phases presented in this document are calibrated using historical temperature data. However, 2023 posed a significant challenge as it deviated substantially from the recorded temperature norms¹, making the models susceptible to anomalous conditions. This anomaly in temperature data has inevitably impacted the performance of the proposed models.

2.1 Phenology detection models

2.1.1 Deep Weather Observation model

The Deep Weather model first described in section 2.2.2.1 of D2.2 and with the updates reported in section 2.2.1.1 of D2.3 is hereby evaluated using 2023 data. The model has been trained on all data available from 2017 to 2022 included. Gaps in the measurements due to weather station malfunction (very common for Tenuta Radici, while extremely rare for all the other pilot plots) have been filled by interpolation when missing a single sample or by unbiasing of neighbouring weather stations with publicly available data when the gaps are longer. The model shows a performance worsening respect to D4.6, due the aforementioned exceptionality of 2023.

Table 3 - Evaluation of Deep Weather model in 2023.

Absolute Error (Days)						
Cultivar / Phase	Bud Break	Blooming	FruitSet	Veraison	Ripening	Average
Aranyo Syrah	5	2	1	13	15	7.2
Ataide Touriga Franca	7	7	/	4	6	6
Ataide Touriga Nacional	4	6	/	5	5	5
Bomfim Touriga Franca	3	1	8	1	9	4.4
Bomfim Touriga Nacional	1	1	5	0	8	3
Tenuta Radici Aglianico	11	7	13	3	17	10.2
Average	5.17	4	6.75	4.33	10	6

As in the deliverables D2.3, D2.4 and D4.6, the performance is compared to the one produced by a GDD (Growing Degree Days) model calibrated using the same data, showing that the Deep Weather Observation model has a lower absolute error on average (6 against 6.25) although the

¹ <https://climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus-2023-hottest-year-record>

performance margin narrows in respect to D4.6 containing validation on 2022 data (Table 3, Table 4).

Table 4 - Evaluation of GDD on weather station data in 2023.

Absolute Error (Days)						
Cultivar / Phase	Bud Break	Blooming	FruitSet	Veraison	Ripening	Average
Aranyo Syrah	15	3	4	10	17	9.8
Ataide Touriga Franca	4	3	/	5	9	5.25
Ataide Touriga Nacional	2	3	/	7	9	5.25
Bomfim Touriga Franca	4	3	11	3	9	6
Bomfim Touriga Nacional	5	3	11	1	9	5.8
Tenuta Radici Aglianico	1	3	9	4	8	5
Average	5.17	3	8.75	5	10.17	6.25

As a further comparison between the presented services and literature approaches, two more models specifically developed for grapevines were implemented, the Grapevine Flowering Veraison (GFV) and Grapevine Sugar Ripeness (GSR) model. The GFV model has been previously used to characterise the thermal times at which flowering and veraison occur for a wide range of cultivars (Parker, A., García de Cortázar-Atauri, I., van Leeuwen, C., & Chuine, I., 2011) (Parker, A. et al., 2013). More recently, the GRS model was developed to characterise the thermal times needed to reach six different target sugar concentrations (170, 180, 190, 200, 210, 220 g/L) (Parker, A et al., 2020).

The GFV is a linear model that uses a base temperature of 0 °C and starts accumulating thermal time from the 60th day of the year (in the Northern Hemisphere) until the appearance of the target phenological stages (50% flowering and veraison). Similarly, the GSR model uses a base temperature of 0 °C and starts the accumulation on the 91st day of the year (in the Northern Hemisphere) until a specific sugar concentration is reached in the berries (as defined in D4.1, section 2.1.3.1).

While a year alone is insufficient to draw meaningful conclusions, it appears that GFV's performance is similar or slightly worse in respect to both the Deep Weather and GDD models, while GSR is slightly better respect to both (Table 5).

Table 5 - Evaluation of GFV and GSR on weather station data in 2023.

Absolute Error (Days)			
Cultivar / Phase	Blooming (GFV)	Veraison (GFV)	Ripening (GSR)
Aranyo Syrah	8	7	11
Ataide Touriga Franca	7	6	11
Ataide Touriga Nacional	6	8	11
Bomfim Touriga Franca	2	0	3
Bomfim Touriga Nacional	2	1	3
Tenuta Radici Aglianico	8	0	9
Average	5.5	3.67	8

To compare finally the 3 models, the cross validation on 2017-2023 is hereby reported:

Table 6 - Evaluation of Deep Weather Observation Model on 2017-2023

Mean Absolute Error (Days)						
Cultivar / Phase	Bud Break	Blooming	FruitSet	Veraison	Ripening	Average
Aranyo Syrah	7.00	3.43	4.86	7.57	6.43	5.86
Ataide Touriga Franca	7.29	3.86	/	4.29	7.14	5.64
Ataide Touriga Nacional	9.00	3.86	/	7.14	6.71	6.68
Bomfim Touriga Franca	5.71	2.71	7.67	3.71	5.57	5.08
Bomfim Touriga Nacional	4.71	2.29	8.00	3.00	6.00	4.80
Tenuta Radici Aglianico	6.29	1.86	4.86	1.57	9.29	4.77
Average	6.67	3.00	6.35	4.55	6.86	5.42

Table 7 - Evaluation of GDD on 2017-2023

Mean Absolute Error (Days)						
Cultivar / Phase	Bud Break	Blooming	FruitSet	Veraison	Ripening	Average
Aranyo Syrah	8.71	4.86	5.43	8.71	7.57	7.06
Ataide Touriga Franca	4.29	3.14	/	4.14	13.71	6.32
Ataide Touriga Nacional	4.57	3	/	4.71	13.71	6.50
Bomfim Touriga Franca	6.29	2.71	8.67	3.71	12.57	6.79
Bomfim Touriga Nacional	6	3	7.33	2.29	12.57	6.24
Tenuta Radici Aglianico	7.43	3	6.57	6.43	8.83	6.45
Average	6.22	3.29	7.00	5.00	11.49	6.57

Table 8 - Evaluation of GDD, GFV and GSR on 2017-2023

Mean Absolute Error (Days)						
Cultivar / Phase	Bud Break (GDD)	Blooming (GFV)	FruitSet (GDD)	Veraison (GFV)	Ripening (GSR)	Average
Aranyo Syrah	8.71	4.71	5.43	6.71	4.57	6.03
Ataide Touriga Franca	4.29	5	/	4.86	8.43	5.65
Ataide Touriga Nacional	4.57	4.71	/	5.86	8.43	5.89
Bomfim Touriga Franca	6.29	2.29	8.67	3.57	5.29	5.22
Bomfim Touriga Nacional	6	2	7.33	3.57	5.29	4.84

Tenuta Radici Aglianico	7.43	2.86	6.57	3.43	7.86	5.63
Average	6.22	3.60	7.00	4.67	6.65	5.53

The comparison confirms that GFV's performance is not strongly different from standard GDD and is worse or slightly worse than the Deep Weather Observation model, while GSR is indeed much better than GDD (6.65 vs 11.49) and slightly better than the Deep Weather Observation (6.65 vs 6.86). On average, the Deep Weather Observation model is still the most precise (5.42 vs 6.57 vs 5.53). Furthermore, it must always be considered that the potential performances of the Deep Weather Observation model are still not fully realized, as it suffers from the small quantity of the training samples and the absence of a validation set that could allow optimal stopping of the network training.

2.1.2 Deep EO3 model

In this section, we evaluate the Deep Earth Observation (Deep EO3) model described in Section 2.2.1.2 of Deliverable 2.3 on the vegetative season of 2023. The model has been re-trained on all data collected between 2017 and 2022 in pilot vineyards. We did not use any validation data. We tried to reduce the error on the training data as much as possible. The results of the evaluation of this new model are presented in Table 9. The magnitude of the mean absolute error is about two weeks for most of the phenological phases and pilot vineyards, as shown by the overall average error of 11.40 days. When comparing these results with the ones obtained in 2022 vegetative season, it is possible to notice a general worsening of performances. This is probably due to the fact that the machine learning model could not make use of enough training data to be able to provide correct predictions despite the fact that 2023 recorded unusual temperatures, which also led to an abnormal occurrence of phenological phases compared to previous years.

Table 9 - Evaluation result of Deep EO3 model in 2023.

Cultivar	MAE (Days)					Average
	Bud break	Blooming	Fruit-set	Veraison	Ripening	
Aranyo Syrah	13	14	16	3	12	11.60
Ataide Touriga Franca	6	9	14	18	28	15
Ataide Touriga Nacional	10	9	12	18	22	14.20
Bomfim Touriga Franca	5	5	1	13	12	7.20
Bomfim Touriga Nacional	15	7	3	16	1	8.40
Tenuta Radici Aglianico	11	11	15	3	20	12
Average	10	9.17	10.17	11.83	15.83	11.40

As in Deliverable 2.3, the Deep EO3 model performances have been compared with the GDD baseline model in 2023. The GDD thresholds have been computed considering data between 2017 and 2022 and have been used to predict the occurrence of phenological phases for pilot vineyards in 2023, reporting the results in Table 10. Unlike the Deep EO3 model, GDD shows most of the time an absolute error greater than a week, remarked by the overall error of 15.21

days. Two factors are worth noticing about these results. In first place, the GDD model results have greater variability than those obtained in 2022 but remain better overall despite the anomalous temperatures in 2023, thus proving to be a less sensitive method to this factor than the DeepEO3 model. Secondly, it can be seen that the GDD model does not provide a prediction for the occurrence of ripening on the Tenuta Radici field and that consequently the mean error values calculated on the ripening phase, on the Tenuta Radici field and the overall error do not take this prediction into account. Overall, it is possible to say that the DeepEO3 model maintains better performance in detecting the occurrence of phenological phases than the GDD model.

Table 10 - Evaluation results of GDD model with satellite data in 2023. (*) means incomplete averages because GDD model does not provide a prediction for the occurrence of ripening on the Tenuta Radici.

Cultivar	MAE (Days)					
	Bud break	Blooming	Fruit set	Veraison	Ripening	Average
Aranyo Syrah	5	19	24	12	2	12.40
Ataide	18	4	10	2	9	8.60
Touriga Franca						
Ataide	15	1	7	4	5	6.40
Touriga Nacional						
Bomfim	10	10	74	60	36	38
Touriga Franca						
Bomfim	11	12	21	2	22	13.60
Touriga Nacional						
Tenuta Radici Aglianico	33	3	6	4	N/A	11.50*
Average	15.33	8.17	23.67	14	12.33*	15.21*

2.2 Phenology forecast models

2.2.1 Deep Weather Forecast model

Together with the observation use case discussed in Section 2.1.1, the Deep Weather Forecast model was also evaluated in the forecast paradigm introduced in section 2.2.1.6 of D2.3. Here, the model takes as an input the measurements of the weather stations up to a certain base date, and the corrected weather forecast for the following days. The base date is selected as 7 and 14 days before each phenological event, measuring thus the error of forecasting a phenological stage one and two weeks before its occurrence. The model evaluated here is the same as the one in the Deep Weather Observation model (Section 2.1.1) and is trained on 2017-2022 historical data. Since the sub seasonal weather forecasts are composed by 48 ensemble values, each series is inputted into the model, and as final forecasted date it is considered the median within all those produced. Whenever the model is unable to forecast the phase date within the weather forecast range for an ensemble series, it is considered as having an error of 28 days.

Table 11-Absolute errors (in days) of Deep Weather model according to number of forecasted days in 2023

Variety	Absolute Error (Days)						
	Forecasted days	Bud Break	Blooming	Fruit-set	Veraison	Ripening	Average error
	7	4	2	0	13	15	6.8

Aranyo Syrah	14	4	2	1	13	15	7
Ataide Touriga Franca	7	11	5	/	4	6	6.5
	14	8	8	/	4	7	6.75
Ataide Touriga Nacional	7	5	5	/	4	5	4.75
	14	10	8	/	4	6	7
Bomfim Touriga Franca	7	2	1	8	1	9	4.2
	14	0	0	7	1	9	3.4
Bomfim Touriga Nacional	7	1	1	4	0	8	2.8
	14	1	1	6	0	8	3.2
Mirabella Eclano Aglianico	7	11	7	13	3	13	9.4
	14	11	8	13	4	14	10
Average	7	5.67	3.50	6.25	4.17	9.33	
	14	5.67	4.50	6.75	4.33	9.83	

Table 12-Average number of days of errors, across all varieties, of Deep Weather model depending on number of forecasted days

Forecasted days	Average error
7	5.75
14	6.18

The performances obtained with this paradigm are also compared with those obtained with a GDD approach, showing again that the Deep Weather model gives better results than the GDD irrespective of the number of days of forecasted measures (Table 13, Table 14).

Table 13 Absolute errors (in days) of GDD model according to number of forecasted days in 2023

Variety	Absolute Error (Days)						
	Forecasted days	Bud Break	Blooming	Fruit-set	Veraison	Ripening	Average error
Aranyo Syrah	7	15	2	4	10	17	9.6
	14	15	0	3	9	17	8.8
Ataide Touriga Franca	7	10	4	/	5	9	7
	14	11	9	/	5	5	7.5
Ataide Touriga Nacional	7	6	3	/	7	9	6.25
	14	11	8.5	/	7	5	7.88
Bomfim Touriga Franca	7	4	2	11	3	9	5.8
	14	1	2	11	3	9	5.2
Bomfim Touriga Nacional	7	4	2	11	2	9	5.6
	14	1	2	11	1	9	4.8
Mirabella Eclano Aglianico	7	1	4	9	4	14	6.4
	14	3.5	5	9	5	28	10.1

Average	7	6.67	2.83	8.75	5.17	11.17	
	14	7.08	4.42	8.50	5.00	12.17	

Table 14 Average number of days of errors, across all varieties, of GDD model depending on number of forecasted days

Forecasted days	Average error
7	6.78
14	7.35

As for the detection model, the results are also compared against GFV and GSR models (Table 15).

Table 15 - Absolute errors (in days) of GFV and GSR models according to number of forecasted days in 2023

Absolute Error (Days)				
Variety	Forecasted days	Blooming (GFV)	Veraison (GFV)	Ripening (GSR)
Aranyo Syrah	7	8	7	11
	14	8	6	11
Ataide Touriga Franca	7	8	6	10
	14	10	6	8
Ataide Touriga Nacional	7	7	8	10
	14	9.5	8	8
Bomfim Touriga Franca	7	2	1	3
	14	4	1	4
Bomfim Touriga Nacional	7	2	1	3
	14	4	1	4
Mirabella Eclano Aglianico	7	8	0	11.5
	14	9	0	13
Average	7	5.83	3.83	8.08
	14	7.41	3.67	8

2.3 Mechanistic model

Deliverable D2.2 presented the Mechanistic model which simulates the advancement of each phenological stage as a function of the main environmental variables influencing all the plant physiological processes, i.e., temperature, soil water availability and solar radiation. The service runs on a daily time resolution starting from January 1st until the present day using on-site weather station data provided by end-users and continues to simulate the progression of the phenological stages using sub-seasonal (next four weeks) forecasts provided by BSC.

Building upon the calibration presented in 2.2.1.5 of D2.3, the model has been recalibrated and validated using the new datasets for the 2023 growing season. As already explained for the other phenological services, the proposed model has been trained and validated using the Cross-validation method, i.e., each year of data (between 2017 and 2023) is selected as validation data, and the model is trained on the remaining six years. The model performance is then estimated as the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) between prediction and observation, averaged

among all the validation runs (one for each year). Cross-validation results for the Mechanistic model are reported in Table 16.

Table 16 Results of the cross-validation of the Mechanistic model evaluated as Mean Absolute Error (MAE).

Average MAE (in days)						
Cultivar / Phase	Bud Break	Flowering	Fruit Set	Veraison	Ripening	Average
Aglianico (Tenuta Radici)	8.0	5.0	6.7	5.9	8.6	6.8
Greco (Tenuta Radici)	3.8	3.8	5.0	14.8	7.0	6.9
Syrah (Aranyó)	3.7	4.6	4.7	7.3	8.9	5.8
Touriga Franca (Quinta do Ataíde)	6.7	5.0	no data	6.0	8.7	6.6
Touriga Franca (Quinta do Bomfim)	3.0	3.6	1.7	3.7	5.3	3.4
Touriga Nacional (Quinta do Ataíde)	7.4	3.7	no data	7.3	8.4	6.7
Touriga Nacional (Quinta do Bomfim)	1.9	4.3	4.0	6.4	7.9	4.9
Average	4.9	4.3	4.4	7.3	7.8	5.9

Moreover, the Mechanistic model was evaluated in the forecast paradigm introduced in 2.2.1.6 of D2.3. To test the effectiveness of the model to predict each phase several days in advance, thus providing useful information to the end user, this set of simulations use in filed weather station data up to 7 and 14 days before each observed phenological event and the weather forecasts for the following days. It has to be noted that sub seasonal forecasts are provided as an ensemble of 48 simulations, thus the phenological predictions are evaluated as the average of the different outputs. For reference, the “0 forecasted days” corresponds to simulation results using only in filed weather station measured data, as it were a detection model.

reports the average Mean Absolute Error between observations and simulations of all the calibrated varieties according to the number of forecasting days (0, 7 and 14). Table 18 shows the average error among all varieties for each forecasting time.

The presented results for the year 2023 show some variability of performance between the different varieties. The predictions for Aglianico in Tenuta Radici (Italy) were fairly poor and significantly higher than the average results of the cross-calibration presented in Table 16, with similar results also for Touriga Franca in Quinta do Ataíde.

For the Greco variety, the model could predict most of the phases with an error around 5 days, with the exceptions of flowering and fruit set regardless of the forecast length. In general, the model was in line with the average results of the cross-calibration for this variety.

The phenological forecasts for the Syrah variety showed an average error that increased from 5 to 6.3 days, on average, between 0 and 14 days of weather forecast.

The best forecast results were obtained for the Portuguese varieties, especially in Quinta do Bomfim. Touriga Nacional simulations in Quinta do Ataíde were in line with the average results of the cross-calibration, increasing from 6.5 to 8.2 days between 0 and 14 days of weather forecast. The best results by far were recorded for both Touriga Franca and Nacional in Quinta do Bomfim. Touriga Franca simulations average an error around 3.2 days regardless of the forecast length, whereas Touriga Nacional starts with an average error of 2.2 without weather forecasts and increases to 2.3 and 2.5 with 7 and 14 days forecasts, respectively.

Overall, compared to simulations performed with weather station data (0 days of forecast), on average the error increases by less than one day, thus most of the source of error in the predictions comes from the base calibration of each variety's parameters.

Table 17 Mean absolute errors (in days) of the Mechanistic model according to number of forecasted days in 2023.

Cultivar / Phase	Forecast days	Bud Break	Flowerin g	Fruit Set	Veraison	Ripening	Average error
Aglianico (Tenuta Radici)	0	14	9	18	1	13	11.0
	7	14.0	9.0	18.0	1.0	12.8	11.0
	14	14.0	9.0	18.0	0.7	12.4	10.8
Greco (Tenuta Radici)	0	5	7	16	4	5	7.4
	7	5.0	7.0	16.0	3.3	4.6	7.2
	14	4.4	7.4	16.0	3.7	4.5	7.2
Syrah (Aranyó)	0	2	8	5	4	6	5.0
	7	3.1	8.1	5.1	4.0	6.0	5.3
	14	6.0	8.6	5.6	4.2	6.9	6.3
Touriga Franca (Quinta do Ataíde)	0	9	14	/	7	9	9.8
	7	12.7	15.1	/	7.0	9.1	11.0
	14	10.1	-	/	7.1	9.6	8.9
Touriga Franca (Quinta do Bomfim)	0	3	7	0	3	3	3.2
	7	2.9	7.3	0.6	3.0	3.0	3.4
	14	1.3	8.1	0.2	3.3	3.0	3.2
Touriga Nacional (Quinta do Ataíde)	0	6	9	/	5	6	6.5
	7	9.9	10.0	/	5.0	6.1	7.8
	14	10.9	9.7	/	5.4	6.8	8.2
Touriga Nacional (Quinta do Bomfim)	0	1	3	0	0	7	2.2
	7	0.8	3.2	0.6	0.0	7.0	2.3
	14	1.1	4.4	0.8	0.0	6.3	2.5
Average	0	5.71	8.14	7.80	3.43	7.00	6.44
	7	6.91	8.53	8.06	3.33	6.94	6.86
	14	6.83	7.87	8.12	3.49	7.07	6.73

Table 18 Average number of days of error, across all varieties and farms, of the Mechanistic model depending on the number of forecasted days.

Forecasted days	Average error
0	6.4
7	6.8
14	6.7

2.4 Deep Camera

In this section, we evaluate the results of the segmentation model described in Section 2.2.1.3 of Deliverable 2.3 on the images collected in the 2023 vegetative season. Also, for this year,

the images collected in pilot vineyards have not been labelled, so it is not possible to derive quantitative measures of the quality of the developed model. We then perform a qualitative evaluation by manually inspecting some of the collected images, reporting the result in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Prediction of the segmentation model for an image for each installed camera. Segmented in red the grapes, in green the leaves.

Overall, good results are still shown by the model in classifying pixels representing leaves (green blobs in prediction), covering most of the leaf area and at the same time distinguishing them from the grass with few exceptions. The problems affecting the quality of produced segmentation masks mentioned in deliverable D4.6 still apply, being this the exact same model presented in that document.

In the previous Deliverable D2.3, the possibility of using the presented segmentation model, together with some visual indexes, for vineyard lifecycle monitoring was discussed. In order to assess the feasibility of this action, the BRI (Blue Red Index) index evolution in each installed camera was compared with the phenological phases communicated by winegrowers during 2023 vegetative season, reporting the results in Figure 9.

Figure 9 Evolution of BRI index on detected grapes segment for each installed camera

In each plot, the purple color illustrates the progression of the BRI index, evaluated specifically for image segments identified as grapes by the segmentation model. Simultaneously, the extension of the grape segment is depicted in blue, expressed as a percentage of the entire image area. The analysis includes only images captured after the fruit set phase since grape detection is irrelevant before this stage. Despite local fluctuations in each plot, potentially arising from varying illumination conditions and the quality of predictions for individual images, a consistent trend is observed. It is worth noting that the fluctuations in illumination conditions are primarily attributed to the automatic balancing of image parameters and the quality of the camera utilized for image capture. These factors underscore the necessity for further research and advancements in image processing techniques to mitigate the impact of variable illumination conditions on the accuracy and reliability of grape detection. Additionally, for the 2023 data, the index consistently rises from the fruit set until ripening, marking the period when grapes are harvested by vintners and cease to be detected by the model.

Deliverable D4.6 also introduced the possibility of using this index for the detection of the phenological phases related to grape maturity such as fruit set, veraison and ripening. After checking this year's results, we have observed low performances. The reasons for these results can be explained by the still improvable performance of the segmentation model and the high variability of the images even between different years, which impact the value taken by the visual index. To promote further research works on this topic, we released the collected dataset, comprising the original images along with segmentation masks generated by our model ².

In the preceding Deliverable D2.3, we introduced vegetation indices computed on leaf segments extracted from camera images by the segmentation model. This section presents a comparative analysis of the temporal variations in the vNDVI index derived from camera images with the NDVI obtained from Sentinel 2 satellite data. The findings are illustrated in Figure 29. Alongside these plots, we have included the total extent of leaf segments expressed as a percentage of the entire image. Although vNDVI and NDVI indices were expected to exhibit similar temporal patterns for this year, given their shared measurement of vegetation greenness and health, the plots reveal substantial differences, with notable divergences observed across most of the 9 cameras under consideration.

² <https://huggingface.co/datasets/links-ads/grapevista-dataset>

Evolution of VNDVI index in Montemarano Aglianico 2023 0700E7EC

Evolution of VNDVI index in Tenuta Radici Aglianico 2023 0700D64C

Evolution of VNDVI index in Tenuta Radici Greco 2023 0700E7EF

Evolution of VNDVI index in Bomfim Touriga Nacional 2023 0700D52A

Evolution of VNDVI index in Ataíde Touriga Nacional 2023 0700D79D

Evolution of VNDVI index in Ataíde Touriga Francesa 2023 0700E288

Figure 10 Comparison of vNDVI from cameras and NDVI from Sentinel 2 satellite for each installed camera

Several factors could contribute to this inconsistency. The segmentation model, identical to last year's validation, might lack precision in distinguishing between leaves, grapes, and the background, especially under varying illumination conditions. Certain plots exhibit prolonged data gaps due to the absence of leaf segments in model predictions. As mentioned earlier, diverse illumination conditions might have influenced the segmentation model's performance,

along with potential sensor contamination during periods of rain or soil exposure. Furthermore, multiple variables, including atmospheric conditions, could affect the accuracy of the NDVI index. While the vNDVI derived from camera images seems to align, with some fluctuations, with the occurrence of phenological phases, NDVI tends to decrease for most cameras during the peak vegetative stage, rising around and after leaf fall. The spatial resolution of satellite data might impact data quality, as the average values over a relatively large area may be more indicative of ground-level vegetation, including weeds, rather than specific grape plants.

2.5 End-users feedback

The phenology monitoring and forecasting service has received predominantly positive feedback, with a note of caution from end users regarding its accuracy in driving management decisions, especially in ripening. While the service surpasses current baseline and similar services in performance, stakeholders remain hesitant to wholeheartedly recommend it due to occasional inaccuracies.

10. For which phases did you find the VITIGEOSS Phenology services useful?

Figure 11 For which phenological phase the phenology service is more useful according to the end users'

Identified as crucial phases, blooming and veraison tracking, along with budbreak and blooming forecasts (Figure 11), are deemed most useful by stakeholders. Symington Estate's varied climatic experiences over the project duration underscore the need for continued refinement, particularly under extreme conditions encountered in recent years. Indeed, Symington estate experienced extreme condition during the three years of project, having an exceptional warm year (2022), an exceptional cold year (2021) and an exceptional rainy September in 2023 (Table 19).

Table 19 Precipitation and temperature in Symington estates during the last 9 years

Year	Precip.	GSP	Precip.	Temp.	GST	T>35°C	GDD	VPD
	Vitic. Year	Apr-Oct	Sept.	Vitic. Year	Apr-Oct	Vitic. Year	Apr-Oct	N° days
	(mm)	(mm)	(mm)	(°C)	(°C)	(n° days)	(C° units)	(KPa)>6
2015	412	239	47,8	16,3	21,4	53	2439	11
2016	662	305	13	16,5	21,0	57	2352	14
2017	326	81	0	17,0	22,2	59	2607	17
2018	544	218	27	16,1	21,1	42	2368	6
2019	369	170	12,2	16,0	20,5	40	2263	1

2020	513	200	19,6	16,9	21,4	57	2434	11
2021	504	256	77,2	16,3	20,5	32	2254	1
2022	311	217	29,4	16,8	22,1	63	2606	18
2023	632	280	75,6	16,8	21,3	37	2427	6

While the data display proves beneficial, stakeholders express mixed sentiments regarding the presentation of results. While some appreciate access to diverse model outputs, others find it confusing. This highlights the importance of streamlining result presentation for enhanced user experience.

Moving forward, addressing accuracy concerns and fine-tuning the model under extreme conditions are paramount. Additionally, efforts should be directed towards improving result visualization to ensure clarity and user-friendliness. Despite these considerations, stakeholders recognize the service's potential and remain optimistic about its future utility.

3. Deep drone service

The service provides vineyard managers with a tool for monitoring the health status of the vineyard, identifying plant stress and other potential issues before they become widespread, and making data-driven decisions about how to manage their vineyards. The service is described in more detail in deliverable D4.6.

The main advantage of using images taken by Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) rather than satellite images is their resolution. While non-commercial satellite images are typically low resolution (e.g., Sentinel-1/2 resolution is equal to 10 m/px), drone images can reach very high resolutions in the order of a few cm/px. This allows to delineate the vineyard rows and filter out the grass that grows between the rows. Therefore, the vegetative analysis on drone images is more accurate rather than the one on satellite images. However, a disadvantage is the high cost of drone flights, which allows just a few flights during the vegetative season. The use of both sources is useful for continuous and accurate monitoring of the vineyard.

The analysis performed over the drone imagery is:

- **Segmentation:** a deep learning model segments the vineyard rows from RGB drone images, producing a segmentation mask
- **Computation of vegetation indices:** the segmentation mask is used to compute pixel-wise vegetation indexes for the analyzed vineyard image. Specifically: the VDI and NDVI vegetation indexes are computed, already described in deliverable D4.6.

In 2022, the end-users involved in the project conducted 6 drone surveys each during the vegetative season. The analysis was performed on the resulting orthoimages, and the performance of the model and results of the analysis were described in deliverable D4.6.

In 2023, the same number of drone surveys was conducted. The flights were performed in the following dates:

Company	Flight dates
Mastroberardino	2023-06-09 2023-06-29 2023-07-25

	2023-09-06 2023-09-29 2023-10-13
Torres	2023-05-25 2023-06-26 2023-30-06 2023-07-31 2023-08-25 2023-09-07
Symington	2023-05-23 2023-06-14 2023-07-04 2023-07-16 2023-08-01 2023-09-01

3.1 Analysis 2023

The robustness of the segmentation model towards visual heterogeneity among the drone orthoimages has been improved with respect to last year’s model, by means of training the model again with the same training data and a more diverse data augmentation strategy. Specifically, the model is more robust towards shadows projected by tall objects such as trees (as in Figure 12), slightly dry, brown-coloured leaves (as in Figure 13) and does not miss large parts of the vineyard rows, as observed in its previous version (see deliverable D4.6). We note that the model still does not perform well on completely dry leaves; however, we argue that analysing vineyards in late stages of the vegetative season (i.e. when the vines become dry after the harvest) is of minor interest for wine growers.

Figure 12 Robustness towards shadows projected by tall objects (trees)

Figure 13 - Robustness towards brown-coloured leaves

The lack of ground truth data on vineyard segmentation prevents us from extracting quantitative measures about the quality of the output segmentation masks. Nonetheless, by visually inspecting the produced segmentation masks and the downstream vegetation indexes, we can confirm that the quality of the segmentation masks has improved with respect to the 2022 ones.

3.2 Temporal analysis 2023

In this section, a time-series analysis compares the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Leaf Area Index (LAI) measured by Sentinel-2 with the Visible Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (vNDVI) and Vineyard Density Index (VDI) computed over UAV images. It is crucial to consider that the vNDVI is derived from Red-Green-Blue (RGB) imagery, subject to varying light conditions, potentially affecting its reliability. Despite this, a trend correlation between the drone signal and the satellite signal is evident in the three pilot plots (Figure 14, Figure 15, Figure 16). The Leaf Area Index (LAI) measured by Sentinel-2 is an effective means of capturing the vegetation development of the vineyard and the corresponding Vineyard Density Index (VDI) reflects the behaviour of the LAI. This suggests that the VDI may serve as a useful tool for analysing and understanding the growth patterns and density of the vineyard.

Figure 14 Torres: (left) NDVI Sentinel-2 and vNDVI UAV images, (right) LAI Sentinel-2 and Vineyard Density Map (VDM) on UAV images.

Figure 15 *Symington*: (left) NDVI Sentinel-2 and vNDVI UAV images, (right) LAI Sentinel-2 and Vineyard Density Map (VDM) on UAV images.

Figure 16 *Mastroberardino*: (left) NDVI Sentinel-2 and vNDVI UAV images, (right) LAI Sentinel-2 and Vineyard Density Map (VDM) on UAV images.

It is interesting to note how the NDVI in *Symington* and *Mastroberardino* vineyards exhibits a high NDVI and LAI (as recorded by satellite imagery Sentinel-2) in early spring when the vines are not yet fully developed. This behaviour can be attributed to the growth of grass between the rows, as depicted in the figure below, demonstrating that satellite derived NDVI can capture inaccurate information about the vineyard's vegetative state.

Figure 17 *Mastroberardino*. LAI (from Sentinel-2) and VDI (from drone) comparison. The grass between vineyard rows affects the LAI measured by the satellite

This observation highlights a potential limitation of relying solely on satellite-derived indexes for assessing vineyard health and growth. While satellite imagery offers broad coverage and regular monitoring capabilities, it may not always provide accurate insights into vineyard conditions, especially in cases where inter-row vegetation significantly influences the measured NDVI values. Therefore, complementing satellite data with ground-based observations or higher-resolution imagery from UAVs can enhance the accuracy of vineyard monitoring and decision-making processes.

3.3 End-users feedback

The drone service has been appreciated for its optimal technical and scientific outcomes, demonstrating its efficacy in precision monitoring. While current cost constraints limit the frequency of flights per season, stakeholders still find immense value in the service for its ability to deliver accurate and detailed data.

Despite limitations, stakeholders express willingness to recommend the service to others, indicating their confidence in its utility and benefits (Figure 18). As technology advances and costs potentially decrease, the service is poised to become even more accessible and impactful in agricultural monitoring and management.

Overall, stakeholders recognize the significance of the drone service in providing valuable insights and remain optimistic about its future potential for enhancing agricultural practices.

6. For which operations was the VITIGE OSS drone analysis useful?

Figure 18 For which operations was the VITIGE OSS drone analysis useful?

4. Key crop indicators tracking services

The Key Crop Indicators are services aimed to monitor the crop status on a weekly basis during the growing season to assess the vegetation health status, crop productivity, crop water use, and crop nitrogen content. The key crop indicators exist of a series of datasets providing information on the vines with different time intervals. Among those indicators are crop parameters, yield estimation, and crop water demand. The crop parameters and crop water demand are delivered on a weekly basis and the yield estimation per season. The crop parameters calculated include actual biomass production, actual crop evapotranspiration, nitrogen content and Normalized Vegetation Index (NDVI).

The Key Crop indicators have been successfully delivered on a weekly basis for the 2021, 2022, and 2023 season. This chapter will focus on the quality of the key crop parameters data over these past seasons. All the Key crop indicators are fed through the API; Data parameters, Yield forecast information and Crop water demand. The evaluation of the quality of the key crop indicators is done by the team of eLEAF as well as by the end users. Sessions have been held between the eLEAF team and all end users separately to discuss anomalies and possible discrepancies in the data. LINKS has organized the final end-user feedback regarding the services, reflecting on the usage of the information linked to the management practices of the wine producers.

4.1 Key Crop indicators in the platform

The crop parameters are displayed in varies ways, when logging on to the VitiGEOSS platform a user will see a color-coded overview of their fields. In Figure 19 you can find an example for the parameter Biomass production that is selected, see top left. We are looking at the fields of one farm in this case for week 14 2023, we can see that one field shows relatively higher values, two relatively lower and the rest of them coded yellow are within the -15% and +15% of average. This can help prioritize the users' actions. When clicking on a specific field the user can find more in-depth information on the values.

Figure 19 VitiGEOSS platform landing page with an overview of color-coded fields for the parameter biomass production.

When zooming in to one specific field the user finds this page shown in Figure 20. It is possible to select only one of the parameters by clicking on it, the others will disappear out of the graph. It is also possible to select those you would like to compare and to zoom in to a certain period.

Figure 20 Overview of crop parameters for one field over the whole 2022 season.

Per field and per parameter the spatial information is shown in the platform as well, when selecting a field an enlarged version pops out for detail (Figure 21).

Figure 21 Spatial overview per parameter for the selected field, when clicking on one of the smaller maps an enlargement pops up.

4.2 Crop parameters

The crop parameters calculated include actual biomass production, actual crop evapotranspiration, nitrogen content and Normalized Vegetation Index (NDVI). This information is supported by the operational data production structure derived from the ETLook model (Pelgrum et al., 2012). In addition to the processing structure managed in ETLook, there are other parameters derived from the combination of spectral bands captured with the satellite sensor. This is the case for the nitrogen content in canopy and nitrogen content in upper leaf and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI).

Before pushing the data onto the platform, the data is automatically checked on its values and manually checked on unexpected patterns. The team of eLEAF has automated the process of checking on outliers, the team will be notified if a parameter reaches a certain value that has been shown untrustworthy. This starts with the input data and ends with the final datasets shown on the platform.

After the 2022 and 2023 seasons had ended, the eLEAF team organized sessions with all end-users involved in the VitiGEOSS project to run through the season's data. The focus was on weather events, noticeable stress that had been picked up by the farmers and correlation with ground truthing data. The correlation and events on site were picked up well in the dataset. By looking back on past weather events, the users have gained a better understanding of how to interpret their data and translate it to the field.

4.3 Yield estimation

Two machine learning algorithms (Random Forest and Gradient Boosting) were trained on historical grape yield data for prediction and forecasting of the grape yield. The performance of both models at 10-fold cross-validation was similar: coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.58$ (± 0.08), mean absolute error MAE = 9.46 (± 0.08) q ha⁻¹ [quintal per hectare], root-mean-square error RMSE = 12.30 (± 1.14) q ha⁻¹, bias = -0.08 (± 1.49) q ha⁻¹.

RMSE

The addition of weather data slightly improved the metrics. The addition of remote sensing Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 observations did not change the performance. Gradient boosting is recommended for forecasting with the vine age being a variable and planting density (vines ha⁻¹), row orientation and cultivar name being static predictors. Care should be taken when forecasting for fields with a low number of training data points. The models are not meant for usage outside the training areas.

Machine learning (ML) techniques were successfully used to predict and forecast agricultural crop yield (Elavarasan et al., 2018) and grape yield (Sirsat et al., 2019). eLEAF was tasked to develop a machine-learning algorithm for grape yield forecasting.

Consortium members Mastroberardino (MB), Symington (SYM) and Torres (TO) provided historical yield data for ML training together with shape files and additional descriptors: cultivar name, age of vine, planting density (vines ha⁻¹) and row orientation (azimuth) degree (Table 20).

Table 20 The number of data points. * - the number of points that remained after the interquartile range filtering per year and per cultivar.

Producer	N plots	N points*	N years	N cultivars
Mastroberardino (MB)	22	93	6	4
Symington (SYM) Ataide	71	244	5	13
Symington (SYM) Bomfim	88	317	5	8
Torres	10	36	6	7

Additional data included weather input from the ERA5 land dataset and remote sensing data from Sentinel-1 GRD (backscatter coefficient) and Sentinel-2 level-2 (normalized difference vegetation index, NDVI). Mean, median, minimum, and maximum values of the backscatter coefficient and NDVI per plot were taken, smoothed with a 60-day moving average and summed along the growing season. ERA5 values of incoming shortwave radiation, air temperature and vapor pressure deficit were aggregated along the growing season without smoothing. The growing season was considered to start and end in September, an approximate harvest month). In this respect, the growing year was shifted 4 months backward, compared to the calendar year.

Results

During the comparison of the actual yield production values and the predicted ones the model performed quite well in one of the three areas. To measure the deviation of the values, we calculated Standard deviation and the percentage of relative standard deviation calculated by dividing the standard deviation by the mean value of the actual and predicted values.

The deviation is rather big for 2 of the 3 users, the consistency in measuring the data is something to pay more attention to, also to compare the results between the users. One explanation is that the model was trained with previous years' data which had a stable year regarding weather conditions, so the numbers did not differ much per year. Another explanation is that during the training ERA-5 weather data were added to improve the metrics, but they contain an average value of previous years of shortwave radiation, air temperature, and vapor pressure that are also the average values of a bigger area and not area specific. For that we would recommend the weather data that we get for these specific tiles from Geos and not constant values of ERA-5. With that said, in extreme drought or rainfall, the model would perform poorly because it does not contain enough training samples (both from bad yield years and weather data) from periods with extreme weather conditions.

4.3 Crop Water Demand

A Crop Water Demand (CWD) Forecast model has been created and is operational within the VitiGEOSS portal. The result is the expected evapotranspiration (CWD) for the actual crop under optimally irrigated conditions for the upcoming week. The role of this tool is to provide a forecast of the amount of water needed for the crop, taking into consideration the weather forecast for the next 7 days.

The Crop Water Demand can be found among the other crop data components in the portal with a value per week in mm/week (Figure 22 Crop Water Demand view Figure 22).

Figure 22 Crop Water Demand view

The model uses GEOS-5 weather data for the current week evapotranspiration estimates, and weather forecast (MONARCH), retrieved from BSC API, this forecasts for the next 3-days reference evapotranspiration. The result of the calculations made (see deliverable 2.2) is the expected evapotranspiration (CWD) for the actual crop under optimally irrigated conditions for the upcoming week. The Crop Water Demand forecast is provided for 7 days ahead. The Crop water demand forecast is provided in cubic meters per management unit, based on the raster information the average management unit value will be calculated.

For the implementation of this model, the short-term forecast is used to create maps for the coming three days, which will be used as input of the forecast. Additionally, the resolutions of the data have been adjusted as the short-term forecast is based on one kilometre resolution and the resolution used for the potential and reference evapotranspiration is 10 meters.

The crop water demand data is checked for anomalies before uploading, the focus is on the trendline of the data compared to previous weeks. When data spikes occur the weather forecast is the first place to look for events. The forecast over the 2023 season has been matched with the weather forecast and a good correlation was visible. The deviations that could be found or questions that came in were mostly due to a change in weather forecast during the week. The Crop Water Demand was uploaded together with all other Key Crop Indicators once a week. A

continuous re-calculation daily could be a potential solution for a more flexible dataset that responds quicker to the weather forecast changes, which is the main driver of this data service.

4.4 End-users feedback

The key crop indicators tracking service has garnered positive feedback for its usability and usefulness. Stakeholders emphasize the importance of clear data translation to the field, especially for new users, to facilitate understanding and interpretation. While ET data quality is praised, it was rather new at the start of the project and required experience to work with. There are performance issues in yield estimation due to insufficient data for accurate modelling.

Positive remarks are directed towards intuitive spatial data visualization and efficient map layering, enhancing user experience and ease of use. However, challenges arise in validating the accuracy of visualized information, particularly regarding intra-parcel variability data. In the case of Torres, they highlight the utility of map-format intra-parcel variability data for vineyard management but notes discrepancies in platform values compared to their own calculations. The service adopts no crop coefficient (K_c) and bases the data on near real time monitoring, while Torres applies their own K_c values that more closely reflect the specific conditions of their vineyards. To address these management differences, a comprehensive approach to data validation and user education is recommended. Incorporating specific vineyard-level data for validation and ensuring alignment between platform values and user-specific calculations, like Torres' custom K_c values, can enhance accuracy and tailor-made data services across diverse viticultural regions.

5. Disease forecast and management services

To proceed with the evaluation of the Downy mildew (DM) and Powdery mildew (PM) disease risk models, these were calibrated with all incidence percentage data obtained during the years 2021 and 2022 (training set) and their accuracy was assessed with data obtained during 2023 (test set).

Throughout 2023 it could be seen that the classification methodology addressed in deliverable D.4.6. was not satisfactory, as end-users were reporting infection events that were not being detected by the models. Therefore, the models were redirected to regression algorithms, which indeed started to show better accuracy than the classification models developed in previous years. The Gradient Descent algorithm was added with the intention of complementing the original development and it was also decided to simplify the Deep Learning model, leaving it as an ordinary MultiLayer Perceptron to see if a simpler architecture would provide more adequate metrics in these particular cases.

Being regression models, in this deliverable the accuracy of the models is expressed as Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of the percentage of disease incidence on leaves, which ranges from 0 to 100%. The MAE measures the average absolute error between predictions and actual values, so the metrics provided in the following tables refer to the average observed error between the actual field incidence and the incidence predicted by each of the models. Although it is not the objective of this deliverable and as a reference to elaborate an informed discussion, the data corresponding to the 2022 model assessment are provided, since they are different with respect to D4.6. and therefore, their results are different as well.

To avoid altering the structure of the graphical interface, the model outputs are automatically translated into qualitative risk as follows: low risk (predicted incidence $\leq 0.5\%$), medium risk ($0.5\% < \text{predicted incidence} \leq 10\%$) and high risk (predicted incidence $\geq 10\%$). The reason for setting the high risk at around 10% of the incidence is that it could be observed that this is the approximate figure at which all growth curves reach the exponential phase and therefore it is understood that the fungus has already started with secondary infections in its haploid stage. Another change with respect to D.4.6. is that the treatment recommendation models were simplified (no treatment, preventive treatment, curative treatment) and adjusted to the level of risk, but no recommendation to apply a particular chemical compound was given since end users used different treatments from each other and rarely repeated from year to year. The dosage does continue to be adjusted to their own needs and to the phenological stage of the plant.

5.1 Model validation during the 2023 season

This section will be focused on the performance of the service during the 2023 season comparing recorded data with predicted data.

The following figures show the results of the models in two parcels, the plots correspond to the seasonal, sub-seasonal and short-term models' outputs during the course of the year in terms of leaf disease incidence. The real data collected is also shown on the plots to compare with the predicted data.

The first results (Figure 23) correspond to the one of the parcels for powdery mildew. As it can be seen on the graphics, the incidence of the disease on the leaf area has happened in a sudden increase, between weeks 16 to 18, the values have gone from 0% to 95% (max) incidence, which is an uncommon behaviour. The response of the models, as it can be observed, does not correspond to the real data in terms of incidence of the disease, but it is accurate in the starting moment of the disease appearance.

Figure 23 Real leaf disease incidence vs predicted leaf disease incidence 2023 results for seasonal, sub-seasonal and weather models on the first parcel

The second results (Figure 24) correspond to a second parcel for powdery mildew. As it can be seen on the graphic, there has been no appearance of the disease, so the recorded incidence by the user is always 0%. The models in this case also predict no appearance of the disease, corresponding to the actual behaviour of the infection.

Figure 24 Real leaf disease incidence vs predicted leaf disease incidence 2023 results for seasonal, sub-seasonal and weather models on the second parcel

5.2 Models retraining with 2023 data

This section presents the metrics of the models retrained with 2023 data. We separate the short-term, sub-seasonal, and seasonal models since they have a different set-up and forecast a different timeframe.

5.2.1 Short-term models

The results of the DM models are reasonable and desirable, presenting a low error between observed ($\sigma = 3.873$) and predicted ($\sigma = 3.303$) incidence. However, the metrics of the PM models show clear signs of overfitting due to the significant difference between the training set ($\sigma = 4.875$) and test set ($\sigma = 15.669$) errors (Table 21. Table 21).

In this case, the models that show better metrics for DM and PM are Decision Tree and Support Vector Machines, respectively, although the Multilayer Perceptron shows low and reasonable errors for both models. Still, the high prediction error in the case of PM requires a larger data collection to be corrected.

On a positive note, a reduction in overfitting and prediction error after adding more data to the training set is evident when compared to the 2022 validation (Table 22).

Table 21. Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of the Downy and Powdery mildew incidence of the short-term regression models for the year 2023.

	Downy mildew	Powdery mildew
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	Train	Test	Train	Test
Decision Tree	2.749	2.382	5.032	15.367
Random Forest	2.958	3.235	5.034	15.419
Gradient Boosting	3.036	4.234	5.253	15.667
K-Nearest Neighbors	2.909	4.197	5.303	15.331
Support Vector Machines	4.899	0.003	3.301	16.105
Gradient Descend	8.114	6.405	5.996	16.270
Multilayer perceptron	2.446	2.668	4.204	15.523

First signs of overfitting of the models in the case of PM, where the training data are memorized and generate failures in the predictions when new data are added (Table 22). This fact was due to the low presence of this pathogen in the fields monitored during 2021.

Table 22. Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of the Downy and Powdery mildew incidence of the short-term regression models for the year 2022.

	Downy mildew		Powdery mildew	
	Train	Test	Train	Test
Decision Tree	5.934	2.426	0.000	4.144
Random Forest	8.352	2.915	0.000	4.144
Gradient Boosting	7.808	4.031	0.000	4.144
K-Nearest Neighbors	6.509	2.105	0.000	4.144
Support Vector Machines	7.351	8.509	0.000	4.144
Gradient Descend	11.989	6.886	0.000	4.144
Multilayer perceptron	6.177	1.429	0.066	4.257

5.2.2 Sub-seasonal models

Again, a good performance of the models for DM in the sub-seasonal horizon can be appreciated, both in the training set ($\sigma = 4.635$) and in the test set ($\sigma = 3.525$) and an over-fitting in the PM models (σ train = 4.825 vs. σ test = 15.498) as it happened with the short-term models due to the scarcity of data for their training. (Table 23). In this case, the most appropriate model for DM seems to be Gradient Boosting and for PM the Support Vector Machines model, although, as in the previous section, the Multilayer Perceptron seems to offer adequate metrics for the prediction of both diseases.

Also, the addition of new data to the training set has improved the metrics with respect to the 2022 validation (Table 24).

Table 23. Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of the Downy and Powdery mildew incidence of the sub-seasonal regression models for the year 2023.

	Downy mildew		Powdery mildew	
	Train	Test	Train	Test
Decision Tree	3.603	3.312	5.379	15.209
Random Forest	3.992	2.210	5.078	15.202
Gradient Boosting	3.614	2.767	5.336	15.483
K-Nearest Neighbors	4.328	3.904	4.922	15.203
Support Vector Machines	4.812	4.126	3.313	15.861
Gradient Descend	7.551	5.482	5.730	15.743

Multilayer perceptron	4.542	2.878	4.020	15.789
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The overfitting in the PM models, which have even less data than the short-term models for calibration, is still very evident (Table 24).

Table 24. Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of the Downy and Powdery mildew incidence of the sub-seasonal regression models for the year 2022.

	Downy mildew		Powdery mildew	
	Train	Test	Train	Test
Decision Tree	8.767	6.412	0.000	4.264
Random Forest	8.555	7.322	0.000	4.264
Gradient Boosting	9.210	7.405	0.000	4.264
K-Nearest Neighbors	8.647	5.508	0.000	4.264
Support Vector Machines	6.411	3.666	0.000	4.264
Gradient Descend	11.400	7.181	0.000	4.264
Multilayer perceptron	6.625	0.367	0.079	4.480

5.2.3 Seasonal models

The trend observed in previous sections is again observed at the seasonal level, where the performance of the DM models is adequate both in the training set ($\sigma = 4.894$) and in the test set ($\sigma = 4.137$), a high overfitting is observed in all the models trained to detect PM incidence ($\sigma_{\text{train}} = 4.706$ vs. $\sigma_{\text{test}} = 16.029$) (Table 25) and an evident reduction in the prediction error is perceived after the addition of new data with respect to the 2022 validation (Table 26).

The Decision Tree shows the lowest prediction error in the case of DM and the Support Vector Machines in the case of PM. Although, in the case of wanting to operate with a single model, the Multilayer Perceptron again shows quite acceptable metrics.

Table 25. Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of the Downy and Powdery mildew incidence of the seasonal regression models for the year 2023.

	Downy mildew		Powdery mildew	
	Train	Test	Train	Test
Decision Tree	1.794	0.000	5.357	15.500
Random Forest	5.435	2.899	4.391	15.500
Gradient Boosting	3.729	16.110	4.723	17.627
K-Nearest Neighbors	4.521	0.000	4.415	15.500
Support Vector Machines	5.473	0.000	3.559	15.500
Gradient Descend	8.432	5.438	6.679	16.642
Multilayer perceptron	4.872	4.513	3.815	15.938

Table 26. Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of the Downy and Powdery mildew incidence of the seasonal regression models for the year 2022.

	Downy mildew		Powdery mildew	
	Train	Test	Train	Test
Decision Tree	7.083	7.000	0.000	3.611
Random Forest	11.546	3.471	0.000	3.611

Gradient Boosting	10.237	4.324	0.000	3.611
K-Nearest Neighbors	10.440	3.671	0.000	3.611
Support Vector Machines	6.712	0.000	0.000	3.611
Gradient Descend	11.564	8.516	0.000	3.611
Multilayer perceptron	6.474	0.457	0.124	3.907

5.2.4 Service conclusion

Looking at the results generated by the models, the first evidence is that adding new data has improved the 2023 metrics with respect to the 2022 ones and has allowed correcting the overfitting to some extent, since the PM models in the 2023 validation showed some range of error in their training set, while in the 2022 validation it can be seen how they memorized the data in detail.

The years 2021 and 2022 were quite exceptional with respect to previous years due to high temperatures and drought, but 2023 has been a particularly anomalous year that has left lots of rainfall in certain areas (complicating the application of fungicides) and no trace of water in other ones. This fact has also generated abiotic stress in the vines, making them more susceptible to infection. Although validation has been somewhat more accurate in this third growing season, in view of the great PM prediction error, more data (in terms of harvest seasons and/or geographical locations) are strongly recommended to correct these deviations.

Finally, the choice of a single algorithm would facilitate the future model calibration and, apparently, the Multilayer Perceptron is a suitable model to predict these two diseases in all the three-time horizons. The Multilayer Perceptron is known to detect seasonal patterns and adequately complement ARIMA-type time series (Zhang and Qui, 2005; Pelka and Dudek, 2019), which could justify such a good performance at this stage. While it is true that with the addition of new data the metrics have been improving, the choice of the final model should be made with a larger amount of calibration data.

5.3 End-users feedback

The service is regarded by all the end users as an interesting and important tool for the management of their crops, but all agree that the performance of the service is lacking accuracy at its current state. This is mainly due to the low amount of data that the models have been trained with. Also, the disease forecast, and management services encountered challenges stemming from extreme conditions, leading to difficulties in disease prediction, for example, see the sudden increase of disease appearance on Figure 23 during the year. Notably, disease prediction capabilities initially lacked accuracy, resulting in a low-risk assessment for infections like downy mildew and powdery mildew. This led to a "no treatment" approach, adhering to project recommendations. However, visual symptoms of powdery mildew emerged, prompting a reassessment of treatment strategies. Despite efforts to mitigate the outbreak, severe infection resulted in the loss of harvest in affected plots. Lessons learned from these experiences underscore the need of more seasons of data to improve disease prediction accuracy. Collaborative decision-making and adaptability are crucial in responding effectively to emerging threats.

6. Business and sustainability management

6.1 Sustainability indicators

This section shows the changes along three years [2021 - 2023] of yield, water usage and pesticide usage for the control parcels of the project (Table 24). For the sake of privacy, the names of the parcels and end users have been anonymized.

Table 27. Average value increase of the sustainability indicators from 2021 to 2023.

Parcel name	End user	Yield		Water usage		Product usage	
		21 - 22	22 - 23	21 - 22	22 - 23	21 - 22	22 - 23
Parcel 1	EU1	-30,2%	-7,7%	12,5%	-11,1%	28,7%	-7,5%
Parcel 2	EU1	53,1%	-40,8%	12,5%	-11,1%	16,1%	-43,0%
Parcel 3	EU2	11,6%	72,3%	67,5%	-33,1%	131,9%	-
Parcel 4	EU2	-27,3%	102,5%	67,5%	-33,1%	131,9%	-
Parcel 5	EU2	-50,6%	-19,8%	5,9%	No usage	175,2%	-29,7%
Parcel 6	EU2	-34,4%	-36,6%	5,9%	No usage	175,2%	-29,7%
Parcel 7	EU3	-2,2%	-27,5%	248,5%	-24,6%	-26,9%	0,8%
Parcel 8	EU3	-0,1%	23,0%	74,2%	-26,7%	-76,0%	35,4%

The values shown on the table correspond to individual parcels rather than the whole vineyard which would contain an aggregated combination of data from multiple parcels. It is important to note that the use of the VitiGEOSS platform is not the only factor in determining the outcome of the harvest of a land plot: other features such as meteorology or disease appearances have a greater impact on it. Also, the 2021 to 2022 percentages are calculated relative to 2021 data and the 2022 to 2023 percentages are calculated relative to 2022 data.

Firstly, in terms of **water usage** a trend can be seen in the sense that the use of water from 21 to 22 is higher in all parcels across the three countries in comparison with 22 - 23, this is due to 2022 being the hottest year on record in the users' regions, the table shows how in 2023 all the water consumption drops. Some interesting data to focus on is the 248% increase on Parcel 7, this is due to a very low water consumption in 2021 and a high demand on the following year. A similar thing happens for the Parcels 3, 4, and 8, which also present a high increase in 2022.

Secondly, in terms of **yield** there is no clear trend outlined in the data but the most interesting cases can be analysed individually, in Parcel 2 we can see a good increase from 21 to 22, but a big decrease again in 22 to 23, this is due to a weather phenomenon that happened in 2023, during the highest disease vulnerability weeks, it rained a lot in the region, making it impossible to spray (which also correlates with a lower product usage), the EU2 states seem to have different trends, Parcels 3 and 4 go up in yield in a significant way while Parcels 5 and 6 go lower, this might be due to the lower water usage on those parcels (down to no water used in 2023).

Thirdly, in terms of **product usage**, end users 1 and 2 have a significant increase in use of pesticides in 2021 - 2022 especially EU 2, which presents a very high use during 2022, which corresponds to a year with high disease risk, and is followed by a decrease in the following year, especially there is a high drop on Parcel 2, which received a high amount of rain during the treatments season, which prevented the applications. The opposite observations can be done for End user 3, which had a big drop on use of pesticides from 2021 to 2022, followed by a smaller increase in the year 2023.

In conclusion, this table shows the use of different resources during the project years and its effect on the yield, as it can be seen the changes on these parameters are very variable, being able to double and even triple the use or reduction of use of some of the resources from one year to the next. This also showcases the effect that the meteorological differences have on the use of resources, since these past years have been very exceptional in these terms, having a very cold year (2021), a very hot one (2022) and very low rainfall throughout the years.

6.2 Resources and tasks optimization

During the course of 2023 the business task planification service has been active and available for the end users to use it and validate it with their own data. During this period a series of adjustments and improvements have been made to the service to adapt it more accurately to the users' needs. This section will go over all the services' characteristics and its validation during this period, as well as give an overview of all the capabilities of the service at the end of the project.

In order to go over the validation of this capabilities, real data will be used from the various use cases this project has, the following figure corresponds to the soil cleaning process and showcases a few of the most detailed capabilities of the service.

Figure 25 Planification of the task execution as designed by the optimizer showing 4 tasks.

Figure 25 displays the results of a schedule as seen on the platform, in this case, modified to show both the tasks view and the teams' view. This schedule corresponds to the tasks assigned to four working teams in terms of soil cleaning. There are four kinds of tasks applied to four different parcels, giving a total of 16 tasks. The following capabilities of the optimization model are showcased in this example:

- **Different dates for different tasks:** The tasks can be set to be assigned during a specific time frame, in this case the starting day of each of the tasks is the following:
 - *Shredding and fertilization:* 14 November
 - *Herbicide:* 20 November
 - *Cutting:* 28 December

This means the task is supposed to be set after the initial day, which as it can be seen on the results it is respected for all the cases.

- **Specialized teams:** Some of the teams can be limited to perform only certain tasks or work on only certain parcels. In this example, the yellow team is limited to perform

only the tasks of herbicide and cutting, which corresponds to the tasks that have been assigned for it.

- **Different prioritization for each task:** Each of the tasks can be optimized in one of the models' three options: reduce its economic cost, reduce its environmental cost, or make it as early as possible timewise. In this case, all of the tasks are defined as time priority except for the shredding tasks which are set for economical cost reduction, this configuration makes it so all the other tasks (within their time frame) are set to be performed earlier. Also, the shredding is done mainly by the orange team, which has a lowest ratio of cost per hectare worked and thus, it takes longer to be performed since it does not have a time constraint.

The following example showcases the results of grape harvesting, in this case the conditions are different that the previous example: there are two type of tasks, hand harvesting and machine harvesting, each of the parcels has its own working team, but the limitation is that the amount of grapes that can be harvested each day for all the parcels is limited, specifically by 30.000 kg for hand harvesting and 25.000 kg for machine harvesting. Figure 26 showcases both the parcel assignation timeline with different colours for each kind of task, and a daily harvest graph which shows the number of grapes harvested each day along with the maximum limit allowed.

Figure 26 Planification of grape harvesting along with daily input limitations

This example showcases and validates the application of two capabilities of the model:

- **Task definition:** The model allows you to create up to four different tasks, in this example the tasks are manual harvesting and machine harvesting. This allows you to create specific teams that work only on one of the tasks, or teams that work on any number of different tasks.
- **Daily limitations:** The service has the option of limiting the daily operation of each of the tasks, for example, limiting the amount of product to be harvested everyday as seen on the figure above. As it can be seen the optimizer tries to reach the maximum amount daily without exceeding the limitations and finishing as fast as possible.

Continuing in the harvest context, the following figure represents the comparison between the brix degree at which the grape is harvested in real data and in the optimizer simulation, validating another capability:

- Priority scaler:** The user can select a scale if priority for their tasks, prioritizing those with a higher value of this variable. In this case, the priority scaler number represents the brix degree of the grape. The optimizer model tries to execute first the parcels with higher brix degree keeping in mind that the optimal value for this property of the grape is 20.8 (Figure 27).

Figure 27 Brix degree collection comparison between real data and simulation

All the functionalities showcased on this section have been the product of co-creation design with the end users and have been available for them to configure their own scenarios during the course of 2023. These functionalities help to define scenarios much adaptable to the real needs of each company.

6.3 End-users feedback

23. Which VitiGEOSS sustainability KPIs were relevant, according to your experience?

4 responses

Figure 28 Relevant sustainability KPI

The business and sustainability management service has received encouraging feedback, particularly regarding its KPI indicators, which stakeholders find valuable for consolidating essential information into a single platform. There's a shared enthusiasm for further enhancements, such as integrating carbon and water footprint calculations, which would significantly bolster the service's ability to provide a comprehensive sustainability overview.

Moreover, the Resource and Task Optimizer has been met with positivity, especially by Mastroberardino, who found it a useful tool in efficiently managing its vertical shoot position activities and has the intentions of applying it to their harvest process in the following season, while Torres has noted similarities to their existing proprietary systems. This suggests that the model built on this service is a solid foundation which can be built upon to tailor the service even more closely to individual farmer contexts, thus, improving its adaptability to different scenarios.

Overall, stakeholders appreciate the environmental insights provided by the service and recognize its potential to streamline operations. With a focus on continual improvement, including automating data computation and simplifying usage, there's optimism for the service to evolve into an indispensable tool for promoting sustainable vineyard management practices.

7. Conclusion

The VitiGEOSS project is aimed at providing wine producers with a comprehensive range of services that will significantly improve vineyard management. Through the use of innovative technology systems like satellite imagery, in-field sensors, and aerial images, the project aims to provide intelligent services to facilitate access to vital information on vineyard management aspects.

This deliverable presents an overview of the performance of VitiGEOSS services: the weather and climate forecasting service, the monitoring and prediction of plant phenological cycles, the business and sustainability tool, the disease management, and the key crop indicators tracking services. The evaluation of this system was done in the second vegetative season (year 2022) through pilot plots located in Portugal, Spain, and Italy, and showed promising results. Overall, they overcome the traditional methods and helped winemakers make well-informed decisions. A second evaluation will be reported in D4.7 over the third vegetative season (2023) to confirm the result presented in the present document.

Overall, the VitiGEOSS decision support system offers effective tools for enhancing the vineyard management process and has a significant impact on the development of cultivars in vineyards.

29. How likely will you use the VITIGE OSS services in the future?

Figure 29 End users' willingness to use VITIGE OSS

In the journey of developing VITIGE OSS, we encountered various challenges, but our response has been characterized by flexibility and innovation, leading to the emergence of new opportunities like the drone service.

The feedback from end users underscores the optimism surrounding VITIGE OSS (Figure 29). While acknowledging the need for further improvements, particularly in areas like disease forecast, the overall sentiment is one of positivity and anticipation. In the face of climate change, the demand for accurate and reliable services is more pressing than ever. While 2-3 years may not be sufficient to fully exploit the potential of our services, we are proud to offer state-of-the-art solutions and are dedicated to increasing their reliability over time. What sets VITIGE OSS apart is its comprehensive offering, consolidating numerous services into a single platform. Features like sub seasonal climate prediction and key crop indicators are particularly appreciated, setting us apart from existing products on the market.

In a market increasingly focused on tackling the challenges of climate change, there is a growing demand for accurate and versatile solutions. VITIGE OSS is well-positioned to meet these demands, continually striving to enhance our services and provide invaluable support to vineyard managers worldwide. With data collected from the platform in the coming years, we anticipate our intelligent services' models to become even more robust and resilient.

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Climate forecast assessment

Figure A1. Sub-seasonal maximum 2-metre air temperature skill scores (RPSS; in percentage) by forecast week for all initialization dates in 2023 and two locations in Campania (top), Douro (middle), and Catalonia (bottom). Notice the operational service started in February 2023 for this variable.

minimum 2-metre air temperature / RPSS / 1999-2016

Figure A2. Sub-seasonal minimum 2-metre air temperature skill scores (RPSS; in percentage) by forecast week for all initialization dates in 2023 and two locations in Campania (top), Douro (middle), and Catalonia (bottom). Notice the operational service started in February 2023 for this variable.

solar radiation / RPSS / 1999-2016

Figure A3. Sub-seasonal solar radiation skill scores (RPSS; in percentage) by forecast week for

all initialization dates in 2023 and two locations in Campania (top), Douro (middle), and Catalonia (bottom).

Figure A4. Sub-seasonal accumulated precipitation skill scores (RPSS; in percentage) by forecast week for all initialization dates in 2023 and two locations in Campania (top), Douro (middle), and Catalonia (bottom). Notice the operational service started in February 2023 for this variable.

2-metre air temperature / RPSS / 1993-2016

Figure A5. Seasonal 2-metre air temperature skill scores (RPSS; in percentage) by forecast month for all initialization dates in 2023 and two locations in Campania (top), Douro (middle), and Catalonia (bottom).

maximum 2-metre air temperature / RPSS / 1993-2016

Figure A6. Seasonal maximum 2-metre air temperature skill scores (RPSS; in percentage) by forecast month for all initialization dates in 2023 and two locations in Campania (top), Douro (middle), and Catalonia (bottom).

minimum 2-metre air temperature / RPSS / 1993-2016

Figure A7. Seasonal minimum 2-metre air temperature skill scores (RPSS; in percentage) by forecast month for all initialization dates in 2023 and two locations in Campania (top), Douro (middle), and Catalonia (bottom).

solar radiation / RPSS / 1993-2016

Figure A8. Seasonal solar radiation skill scores (RPSS; in percentage) by forecast month for all initialization dates in 2023 and two locations in Campania (top), Douro (middle), and Catalonia (bottom).

accumulated precipitation / RPSS / 1993-2016

Figure A9. Seasonal accumulated precipitation skill scores (RPSS; in percentage) by forecast month for all initialization dates in 2023 and two locations in Campania (top), Douro (middle), and Catalonia (bottom).

